

CAM Services Platform: Managing CAM Services in Multi-Domain Cross-Border Scenarios

J. Baranda*, A. Galal*, A. Mpatziakas[†], A. Sinanis[†], G. Gómez[‡], J. Scholliers[§], S. Karageorgiou[¶], G. Agapiou^{||}, M. M. Alam**, A. Castelli^{††}, A. Drosou[†], M. Payaró*, J. Mangués-Bafalluy*

* Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA);

[†] Centre for Research and Technology (CERTH); [‡] ATOS/EVIDEN Research & Innovation;

[§] VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland; [¶] eBOS Technologies Ltd; ^{||} Wings ICT Solutions;

**Tallin Technical University; ^{††} Brainstorm Multimedia

Abstract—This poster presents the cloud-native CAM Services Platform designed in the context of the EU 5G-ROUTES project to handle the life-cycle management of virtualised CAM services and to assist them during run-time to accelerate its widespread on next generation mobile networks. It is built upon the combination of the so-called technological enablers, designed to consider complex scenarios involving multiple administrative domains and edge deployments derived from cross-border interactions across mobile network operators. The CAM Services Platform is validated in a test environment as a previous step to its integration in a field roll out of 5G mobile networks in Latvia and Estonia.

I. INTRODUCTION

The architecture of 5G/6G networks is experiencing a revolution thanks to novel networking paradigms based on softwarization, like Network Function Virtualization (NFV). This is also allowing the introduction of new stakeholders in the mobile ecosystem, like the vertical industries.

One of such verticals is the automotive industry, which proposes innovative use cases (UCs) related to Connected and Automate Mobility (CAM) scenarios [1]. Such scenarios can present a high degree of complexity when considering cross-border situations and low-latency needs, thus requiring the deployment of CAM network services (NSs) at edge Points of Presence (PoPs) close to end-users. This is the context of EU project 5G-ROUTES [2], whose aim is to accelerate the widespread of 5G end-to-end interoperable CAM ecosystems.

This poster presents the description and validation of the CAM Services Platform (SP). This a cloud-native platform whose aim is to handle the life-cycle management (LCM) of virtualised CAM services in the envisioned complex scenarios. The CAM SP is built upon a set of so-called technological enablers (TEs). They have interfaces to assist virtualised CAM services in a more transparent way than other existing approaches [3], achieving complex procedures like CAM NS relocation across independent administrative domains (ADs) [4].

II. THE CAM SERVICES PLATFORM

The CAM SP is a modular cloud-native solution running on top of the 5G mobile network, as shown in Figure 1. It is built upon a set of TEs, which are distributed across different PoPs (i.e., core, edge) depending mainly on the required latency for their actions. Deployed with the use of an ETSI NFV orchestrator, like Open Source MANO (OSM), they handle the artefact management, instantiation, relocation, and termination

of CAM NS backends, which also run in the same PoPs as the TEs. Examples of developed CAM NS backends in 5G-ROUTES Project [2] are *platoon manager*, *see-through* or *roadworks warning*. An instance of the CAM SP runs in each AD, which implies the communication across TE instances of different ADs to support cross-border scenarios. On top, the Tenant Web Portal (TWP) is the centralized entry point for the different CAM SP instances and also the tool to analyse and visualize the data obtained from the execution of a CAM NS. Currently, there are seven available TEs in a CAM SP.

The *Integration Fabric* [6], based on ETSI ZSM architectural guidelines, consists of an MQTT message-passing broker and the Service Adapter (SA) module, which interacts with OSM to execute the operations arriving through the broker. The defined topic and message structure allow the exchange of orchestration operations across different ADs and the exchange of messages for data-logging purposes. The *CAM Repository* [7] is a registry system handling the catalogues and storage of the required NS artefacts (i.e., container images, Helm Charts, and OSM VNF and NS descriptors). The *Assisted Service Continuity* (ASC) enabler provides information to UEs about running CAM Services backends, helping to reconnect to the suitable CAM service instance in the context of a cross-border situation. The *Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) Broker* is an MQTT/AMQP message-passing broker allowing the exchange of V2X awareness messages (e.g., CAM/DENM/CPM) among vehicles in different ADs. Its topics are organised according to Quadtree tiles and an available GEO location sub-module performs the message distribution.

The *Predictive Resource Allocation Enabler* (PRAE) supports CAM service relocation. It parses CAM messages from V2X Broker and collects resource related data from CAM Repository and IF. Initially, a Deep Neural Network forecasts the position of the tracked vehicles. If a border crossing is predicted, a second Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithm determines the best PoP to launch a new instance of the CAM Service by triggering the IF [5]. The *Low Latency Synchronization* (LLS) TE allows relocating the state of CAM Service backends from the instance running in the initial network to the pairing instance (e.g., after service relocation) in the visited network. It is triggered by the PRAE and follows a hot standby synchronisation strategy. Multiple data

Fig. 1. Architecture of CAM Services Platform, deployment in multiple administrative domains, and its relation with 5G network

reduction methods such as de-duplication and compression are employed to reduce synchronisation time. Finally, the *Object Fusion* (OF) TE performs an object-level fusion and trajectory prediction to provide road actors with a vehicle-infrastructure area perception. It uses the V2X Broker to access CAM and CPM messages and the LLS TE to share data between borders. OF uses a Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture filter to perform the fusion process, publishing the result in the V2X Broker.

III. VALIDATION ASPECTS

To validate the correct interaction among TEs, CAM Service backends, and across domains, we configured a test environment scenario in the CTTC 5G/6G Testbed. The scenario encompasses three physical servers. One runs the TWP in a Kubernetes (K8s) cluster, and the remaining servers implement the different ADs. Each of these servers hosts two VMs containing i) a K8s cluster acting as a NFV infrastructure (NFVI) PoP and ii) an OSM instance. The TEs of the CAM SP are deployed in each K8s with the associated OSM instance. Then, CAM Service backend artefacts are onboarded [7] to have an operational environment. This test configuration serves as a reference and, currently, it is being adapted to be integrated into an ICT infrastructure connected to field trial deployments of 5G networks in Latvia and Estonia.

TABLE I

AVERAGE PROCESSING TIME OF OPERATIONS IN A MULTI-AD SCENARIO

Operation Type	Avg SA Processing Time [msec]	Avg Total Processing Time [s]
Create Network Service	13.02	33.22
Get NFVI Resources	14.20	0.26
Get NS Instance Info	15.26	17.23
Terminate Network Service	14.04	0.76

Table I presents the average time required by the SA to process 100 repetitions of different LCM operations performed using a sample CAM service backend in the remote AD of the test scenario. That is, when operation is sent to the IF of a

given domain to be executed by the SA of the neighbouring domain. The time to execute the operation is in the order of seconds. While the processing done by the SA module is in the order of msec, the vast majority of time is required by OSM to interact with the underlying NFVI.

IV. CONCLUSION

This poster presents the description of the CAM Services Platform designed to assist the LCM of virtualised CAM Services in cross-border scenarios. This platform has been validated in a test environment and it is being integrated on top of a real 5G network deployment between two countries.

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